

Reading Readiness and Performance among Kindergarten Learners

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Abstract:

The study determined the reading readiness and performance among Kindergarten learners. It explored the significant relationship between reading readiness and reading performance and the Kindergarten teachers' and parents' challenges and coping mechanisms in teaching reading. The findings served as the basis for a proposed reading enhancement program that can remedy reading skill deficiencies. The study was anchored on Dr. Arnold Gesell's Maturational Theory and McGinnis & Smith. It employed descriptive-correlational design. It was conducted at the University of San Carlos-North Campus. The 42 Kindergarten learners, Kindergarten teachers, and parents were the research respondents. The learners' reading readiness test, their average grade of the first two quarters in Reading and the results of the interview of the respondents were the research instruments. Results revealed that some children, despite not being ready during the admission, performed better in reading than expected. Others performed lower than expected. The teachers' challenges were high learning expectations in Kindergarten, teaching learners with mixed abilities and giving an emphasis on a standardized test. Parents' challenges were high learning expectations and instilling good study habits and interest in reading. Teachers and parents were able to cope with these challenges through collaborative efforts. The findings suggested that Reading readiness is not the sole determinant in the reading performance of a child. In conclusion, reading readiness is not a sole predictor of reading performance. Teachers' commitment to teaching, the instructional approaches used, learners' attitude and interest to learn, providing remediation and parents' support can improve reading performance.

Keywords: Challenges, Coping mechanisms, Kindergarten Learners, Reading Readiness and Reading Performance

Introduction:

Recognizing how vital early learning of a child is, we can understand the significant prominence of raising awareness on school readiness especially in fostering his or her reading readiness skills. Reading readiness has been termed as the stage when a child is prepared to read and the period of transition from a non-reader to a reader.

Teachers make use of reading readiness assessments to evaluate whether the children have acquired the fundamental skills in learning to read. There are many skills that are considered reading readiness skills such as letter and sound recognition, visual and auditory discrimination, vocabulary and listening skills. All of these skills concurrently help prepare a child to begin to read.

Buendia (2011) revealed that in the School Year 2009-2010, 66.17% of the First Grade pupils in the public schools underwent Early Childhood Education. Furthermore, the result of the School Readiness Year end Assessment (SReYA) of the incoming First Grade pupils showed that only 42% were prepared for formal education.

Flores (2002) stated that surveys have indicated that reading skill difficulty which begins with the First Grade learners is due to lack of reading readiness.

An absence of readiness and the interest to read, a child finds it difficult to acquire the skills necessary for reading just like any other skills Rance (2006).

In the University of San Carlos North Campus, the Kindergarten teachers faced many challenges of teaching children with different learning abilities and learning needs and felt the pressure on how to help the Kindergarten learners

attain high standards of learning, acquire reading fluency skills and to attend to a wide variation of student needs. Learners had different racial and socioeconomic backgrounds. Some learners had formally or informally underwent pre-school education while others had not. There were also learners who required individualized approach to address specific needs. The pressure that the teachers have to teach these learners having varying and wide extent of abilities and needs in a classroom with literacy and numeracy skills also increased.

It was in the School Year 2017-2018, University of San Carlos North Campus did not offer pre-school level and offered only Basic Education. The school admission policy for Kindergarten level was highly inclusive. Otherwise, the number of enrollees would be significantly reduced. The school provided the opportunity of education to applicants, regardless of their academic profile as established in the admission test. Admission test given to Kindergarten applicants was the Intelligence Quotient (IQ) test which served solely as the readiness test. However, the researcher observed that the intelligence test may not seem to be associated with reading. It is not enough to indicate a child's reading skills and it does not likewise measure his or her early learning.

As a PAASCU accredited school, the school followed the standard competencies required by Center for Educational Management in order to match up the standards with all accredited schools. Hence, before the school year ends, Kindergarten learners are required to take the Achievement Test in English provided by Center for Educational Management. Part of the Achievement Test is a rudimentary reading test, which presupposes that the children have already acquired fundamental reading fluency skills. In the last three school years, there was inconsistency of the Kindergarten Learners' performance in the English Kindergarten K to 12 Achievement Test. In the School Year 2014-2015, the Kindergarten learners got a low scaled score and had unfavorable ratings specifically in Grammar and Usage, Vocabulary and Reading Comprehension. In the last two school years, the Kindergarten learners got a higher scaled score than the population scaled score. However, a decline of the total mean scaled score was notable in the recent school year. Results indicated that they consistently showed low performance in vocabulary.

Because of the continually high rate of students who had not acquired the reading skills needed before Grade one, the researcher saw the need to propose a reading enhancement program that would make use of researcher-made reading readiness assessment tool which could determine the baseline performance of the learners. The researcher intended to strengthen the reading skills of the learners and likewise, to decrease prevalence of early reading deficiencies through this research.

Literature Review:

The literature emphasizes that early childhood, particularly the first six years of life, is the most critical period for a child's growth and development. During this stage, cognitive, language, social, emotional, and psychological capacities develop rapidly, making it the ideal time to introduce and strengthen foundational literacy skills. Researchers such as Otto (2008) highlight that children's learning potential is most receptive during these formative years, underscoring the importance of early literacy interventions and reading readiness programs.

The significance of early literacy development has been widely recognized because it serves as the foundation for future academic success. Mena (2008) noted that increasing literacy awareness during early childhood is essential in fostering reading ability. Similarly, Morrison (2006) explained that early childhood education programs contribute not only to children's social, emotional, and physical development but also to the enhancement of communication and literacy skills. These early years are considered the period when reading readiness skills begin to emerge and develop.

In the Philippine educational context, Kindergarten has become a mandatory component of basic education. According to Pastorfide (2016), children aged five are required to complete Kindergarten before entering Grade 1. This policy recognizes the importance of preparing children academically, socially, and emotionally for formal schooling. Early literacy development prior to school entry has also been identified as a significant factor in reducing future academic difficulties. DeBaryshe and Gorecki (2007) stressed that positive literacy experiences and

communication development during the preschool years contribute to intellectual growth and improved academic outcomes.

Reading readiness plays a crucial role in children's educational success. It refers to the developmental stage in which children acquire the necessary skills and maturity required to begin learning to read effectively. UNICEF (2012) describes reading readiness as a sequence of developmental processes that prepare children to transition from non-readers to readers. Akubuilu and Okorie (2015) further argued that readiness is essential for accomplishing any complex task, especially reading, which requires a certain level of cognitive maturity, language competence, and prior learning experiences.

Reading itself is considered one of the most important skills children can acquire because it serves as the gateway to learning in all academic disciplines. Anderson (2003) emphasized that students must be able to read and comprehend texts to make sense of the world around them and to succeed in future learning. Likewise, Otto (2008) identified reading development as a primary objective of early childhood education, particularly during Kindergarten and the early primary grades.

The literature also highlights the concept of emergent literacy. Marie Clay (2010) proposed that literacy development begins long before children enter formal schooling. Children naturally acquire knowledge about language, reading, and writing through their everyday experiences at home and within their communities. This perspective is supported by Strickland and Riley-Ayers (2006), who emphasized that literacy development begins early and is closely linked to later academic achievement. When children's exposure to language and literacy experiences is limited, their likelihood of experiencing future learning difficulties increases.

Numerous studies indicate that deficiencies in reading readiness contribute significantly to reading problems in the primary grades. Flores (2002) found that many reading difficulties observed in first-grade pupils stem from inadequate reading readiness skills. Similarly, Nelson, Palonsky, and McCarthy (2004) noted that children who struggle to develop reading proficiency often experience broader academic challenges, whereas fluent readers tend to perform better across subjects. Bassarewan and Simone (2010) further argued that mastery of reading skills is strongly associated with academic success and lifelong learning opportunities.

The changing nature of Kindergarten education has also influenced literacy expectations. According to Allphin, the skills expected of Kindergarten pupils today are more advanced than those expected in previous generations. Kindergarten has evolved from a primarily social and emotional development program into one that places greater emphasis on academic skills, including reading and numeracy. Morrison (2006) described this transformation as a significant shift that continues to shape curriculum design and instructional practices.

Research also demonstrates the long-term benefits of early childhood education and preschool experiences. MacDonald (2013) found significant differences in letter-naming fluency between children who attended pre-Kindergarten programs and those who did not. Children with prior educational experiences generally enter school better prepared for academic demands and exhibit stronger literacy skills. Semorlan (2015) similarly concluded that early educational experiences positively influence academic performance and facilitate smoother transitions from Kindergarten to Grade 1.

Assessment plays a vital role in monitoring children's reading readiness and literacy development. Hullinger-Sirken (2013) emphasized that readiness assessments help educators identify students' strengths and weaknesses, enabling teachers to provide targeted instruction and support. Assessment data can guide interventions, reduce learning gaps, and ensure that both proficient and struggling readers receive appropriate assistance. DeBruin Parecki (2004) further noted that early literacy indicators such as letter recognition, phonemic awareness, decoding, fluency, and comprehension are reliable predictors of future academic achievement.

The literature consistently stresses the importance of early intervention. Allphin (2011) argued that identifying and addressing reading difficulties during the early years prevents more serious literacy challenges in later grades. Supporting this claim, Driver (2011) found that reading readiness interventions significantly improved children's letter-sound recognition, sight-word recall, and reading comprehension. These findings suggest that targeted literacy programs can effectively strengthen foundational reading skills before formal reading difficulties become entrenched.

The home environment also plays a crucial role in literacy development. Research by Shier (2014) revealed that children whose parents regularly read stories, sing songs, and engage them in literacy-related activities tend to develop larger vocabularies, stronger verbal skills, and better reading abilities. Orillosa (2014) similarly emphasized the importance of home readiness and parental involvement in promoting early literacy development. Such findings support the view that literacy learning begins at home and is reinforced through meaningful interactions with family members.

Furthermore, the role of adults in children's literacy development cannot be overstated. Schwartz, Christian, and Jean (2013) described parents and teachers as natural mentors who significantly influence children's learning experiences. Scales and colleagues (2004) asserted that the quality and extent of adult support directly affect children's developmental outcomes. Parents are recognized as children's first teachers, while classroom educators provide structured opportunities for literacy growth and academic development.

The reviewed literature strongly supports the importance of reading readiness and early literacy development during the formative years of childhood. Reading readiness serves as a critical foundation for successful reading acquisition, academic achievement, and lifelong learning. The studies consistently demonstrate that early educational experiences, supportive home environments, effective assessments, timely interventions, and collaboration among parents, teachers, and caregivers significantly contribute to children's literacy development. Consequently, fostering reading readiness during Kindergarten and the preschool years remains essential for ensuring children's long-term educational success and overall development.

Methodology:

Research Design

The current study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. It examined the relationship between reading readiness and reading performance among Kindergarten learners. This method analyzed the data gathered in order to validate or negate the depth of the association between the Reading Readiness Proficiency level and Reading performance.

Research Respondents

Forty-two Kindergarten learners at the University of San Carlos Basic Education Department who enrolled in the School Year 2017-2018, Kindergarten teachers and parents were the respondents in this study. There were two sections in Kindergarten level namely St. Gabriel and St. Michael. St. Gabriel section had 21 learners with 10 boys and 11 girls. St. Michael section had 21 learners with 10 boys and 11 girls. The Kindergarten teachers were part of the respondents in order to determine some of the challenges they experienced in teaching the Kindergarten learners specifically in reading and at the same to determine their coping mechanism in teaching reading to children with wide ranging abilities. The researcher also included the Kindergarten parents as respondents in this study in order to explore their coping mechanism of their children's learning.

Research Environment

The research was conducted at the University of San Carlos-North Campus which was located at the General Maxilom Avenue, Kamputhaw, Cebu City. The campus is part of the private co-educational sectarian school, University of San Carlos, managed and owned by the Society of the Divine Word (SVD) missionaries. This is a Catholic school of learning that exemplified the philosophies of learning of San Carlos Borromeo and the spiritual values of the Society of Divine

Word in doing the mission. It aims to develop the students to be excellent and socially responsible professionals and lifelong learners in an environment that promotes excellence in the learning processes of teaching-learning, research, and outreach activities.

Research Instruments

Summary of the Reading Readiness Profile

The data showed the summary of the Reading Readiness profile of the learners as established in the Admission test and likewise, indicated the learners' Intelligent Quotient score and the descriptive categories of their Intelligent Quotient scores.

Summary of the Learners' Reading Performance Profile for the First and Second Quarters

The First and Second Quarter Reading Performance Profile showed the learners' reading performance based on the learners' Reading grades in the first and second quarters.

Results based on the interview of the Kindergarten Teachers and Parents

The researcher conducted an interview to the Kindergarten teachers in order to determine the Kindergarten teachers' challenges and concerns about teaching in Kindergarten specifically in reading. The researcher utilized open-ended questions in order to gather full knowledge of the subjects' views and opinions and to obtain profound, significant and helpful answers needed for qualitative analyses.

Researcher also administered an interview to Kindergarten parents to determine their challenges they experienced in teaching their child how to read and the efforts they made to cope with the learning expectations set by the school. Guide questions were used by the researcher in conducting the interview.

Research Procedures

Gathering of Data

The researcher sent a transmittal letter to the School Principal stating the researcher's intention to conduct a study which involved determining the reading readiness and reading performance among the kindergarten learners in the University of San Carlos. The letter also stated that the findings of which would serve as the basis for a proposed reading enhancement program that would enhance the existing reading program. When approved, the researcher gathered the results of the learners' Reading Readiness test from the psychometrician as established in the admission test. The results were recorded in the summary of the Reading Readiness profile in order to analyze the findings and interpret the results qualitatively and quantitatively.

The researcher also gathered the learners' reading performance profile. It denoted the student's achievement in meeting the short- or long-term goals in Reading course content. It encompassed the students' grades in reading in a given quarter. It represented the average grade of the first and second quarter grades. The grading components in reading were consistent with Department of Education grading system. The grade of a student was computed based on the following criteria: 30% Written Activities, 50% Individual Reading Performance and 20% Quarterly Examinations.

The results on the Reading Readiness assessment and the Learners' Reading Performance in the first and second quarters established the significant relationship between reading readiness and reading performance among the Kindergarten learners in the University of San Carlos North Campus.

The researcher conducted an interview in gathering data on the Kindergarten teachers' challenges and concerns they experienced in teaching reading. The researcher employed guide questions to ask each kindergarten teacher. The interview was administered for at least three minutes in the school premises. The respondents' interviews were recorded so that the researcher can gather and make necessary comments and observations based on their answers.

Kindergarten parents were also the respondents in this study. The researcher sent a consent letter to conduct an interview. The objectives and procedure of the study were explained. Furthermore, participants were assured of the confidentiality of their identities and answers in the recorded interview. The researcher also suggested that they were free to express their opinions and feelings on the matter being asked. They were asked to a declaration of informed consent, which were stated in the letter and during the interview. The researcher made use of guide questions to explore on the mechanism used by their children in coping with the learning expectations set to their child at the end of the Kindergarten academic year. Furthermore, parents were also asked on any effort directed to help their child in coping with the learning expectations set by the school. The findings were the bases for recommendations for designing school programs concerning teaching and learning matter.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized in this study for the purpose of testing the research premise. The data gathered from this study were verified using the following statistical tests.

1. The frequency and percentage distribution were calculated to show the profile of the reading readiness proficiency and reading performance of the Kindergarten learners.

$$p = \frac{f}{n} \times 100\%$$

where :

p= percentage

f= frequency

n= number of cases

2. The researcher employed Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient to determine the significant relationship between reading readiness and reading performance among the Kindergarten learners.

$$r = \frac{\sum XY - \frac{(\sum X)(\sum Y)}{n}}{\sqrt{\left(\sum X^2 - \frac{(\sum X)^2}{n}\right) \left(\sum Y^2 - \frac{(\sum Y)^2}{n}\right)}}$$

where:

r = correlation value

x = score in reading readiness

y = score in reading performance

n = number of Kindergarten learners

In using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient, the data were recorded using Microsoft Excel and analyzed with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient measured the strength or weakness and positive or negative association that exists between two variables measured in this study on at least an interval scale. This method tried to understand whether there was an association between reading performance and reading readiness. In this case, the statistical method that was used to analyze question 3 drew an outcome on an association or indirect association between reading readiness and reading performance.

The researcher explored the significant relationship between reading readiness and reading performance among the Kindergarten learners in the University of San Carlos-North Campus.

The researcher made use of an interview method to determine the Kindergarten teachers' and parents' challenges and concerns in teaching reading as basis for qualitative analyses. It further explored on the efforts made by the teachers and parents to help the child cope with the stated learning standards in Kindergarten. The insightful

comments made by the respondents helped in the qualitative interpretations and in making analyses of this study. Findings and conclusions of this study served as a basis for the recommendations of specific interventions and modifications in respect to admission policy, teaching-learning practices, educational theory, or subsequent research.

Results and Discussion:

This study examined the relationship between reading readiness and reading performance among Kindergarten learners. It also explored the challenges encountered by teachers and parents in developing children's reading skills and identified the coping mechanisms they employed to address these challenges. The findings were derived from quantitative data on learners' reading readiness and reading performance, as well as qualitative data gathered through interviews with teachers and parents.

Reading Readiness of Kindergarten Learners

The results revealed that the majority of the Kindergarten learners demonstrated satisfactory levels of reading readiness. Out of the 42 learners who participated in the study, 33 learners or 79% were classified as "Ready," 5 learners or 12% were categorized as "Very Ready," while only 4 learners or 9% belonged to the "Not Ready" category.

These findings indicate that most learners possessed the intellectual and reasoning abilities expected of children at their developmental stage. The reading readiness assessment utilized the Otis-Lennon School Ability Test (OLSAT), which measured cognitive abilities such as critical thinking and reasoning skills. The predominance of learners in the "Ready" category suggests that the majority had acquired the necessary cognitive foundations for formal schooling and literacy development.

Several factors may have contributed to these positive results. Many of the learners had prior preschool experiences that exposed them to early literacy activities and learning opportunities before entering Kindergarten. Such experiences likely enhanced their language development, reasoning abilities, and readiness for academic tasks. Additionally, parental involvement may have played a significant role. Children who are frequently exposed to storytelling, reading sessions, songs, and other literacy-related activities at home are more likely to develop stronger cognitive and communication skills.

The findings support the literature emphasizing the importance of early childhood education in developing reading readiness. According to DeBaryshe and Gorecki (2007), early cognitive, social-emotional, and literacy development significantly contribute to a child's preparedness for school. Morrison (2006) likewise highlighted that early childhood education programs provide opportunities for developing foundational literacy and language skills that prepare children for future learning.

However, a small percentage of learners were classified as "Not Ready." These learners obtained lower scores in the reading readiness assessment, indicating that they had not yet fully developed the intellectual maturity and language skills expected at the Kindergarten level. Several possible explanations may account for this finding. These learners may have had limited exposure to literacy activities before entering school, fewer opportunities for cognitive stimulation, or insufficient adult support during their formative years.

The results underscore the critical role of parents and caregivers in fostering children's readiness for learning. Since parents are children's first teachers, their involvement in literacy-related activities significantly influences children's cognitive and language development. Learners who lack such support may require additional interventions and guidance to help them develop the skills necessary for academic success.

Overall, the findings suggest that most Kindergarten learners possessed adequate cognitive readiness for learning, which may be attributed to preschool experiences, supportive home environments, and exposure to literacy activities before entering formal education.

Reading Performance of Kindergarten Learners

The study also examined the reading performance of the learners. The results showed that most Kindergarten learners demonstrated satisfactory to outstanding performance in reading.

Among the 42 learners, 12 learners or 29% were classified as "Advanced," obtaining grades of 90% and above. Sixteen learners or 38% were categorized as "Proficient," earning grades between 85% and 89%. Eight learners or 19% were classified as "Approaching Proficiency," while four learners or 9% belonged to the "Developing" category. Only two learners or 5% fell under the "Beginning" level.

These results indicate that a substantial majority of the learners successfully acquired the expected reading competencies for their grade level. The combined percentages of learners in the Advanced and Proficient categories demonstrate that most students exceeded or met the required learning standards in reading.

Several factors may explain this positive performance. One significant factor is the dedication and commitment of teachers to implementing effective reading instruction. Teachers' passion for teaching, consistent implementation of reading programs, and commitment to student learning may have contributed greatly to the learners' success. Previous studies have shown that passionate and committed teachers positively influence student achievement and motivation to learn.

The instructional approaches employed by teachers may have also played a vital role. Teachers provided meaningful learning activities that connected new knowledge with learners' prior experiences. Such practices align with Ausubel's Subsumption Theory, which emphasizes meaningful learning through the integration of new concepts with existing knowledge.

Another contributing factor is the implementation of remediation programs. Learners who experienced difficulties in reading received additional support through remedial instruction. These programs provided targeted interventions that addressed specific learning gaps and helped struggling learners improve their reading skills. Remediation also reassured parents and learners that improvement was possible despite initial challenges.

Differentiated instruction further contributed to improved reading performance. Teachers adapted lessons according to learners' individual abilities, learning styles, and pacing. By providing varied activities and instructional strategies, teachers were able to accommodate diverse learner needs and promote meaningful learning experiences.

Parental involvement also emerged as a significant factor. Teachers regularly communicated with parents regarding learners' progress and provided feedback on areas needing improvement. Parents reinforced learning at home by assisting with reading activities, reviewing worksheets, and practicing reading skills. Such collaboration between home and school strengthened learners' literacy development and encouraged positive reading habits.

Additionally, learners' motivation and positive attitudes toward learning influenced their performance. Children who displayed enthusiasm and interest in reading were more likely to engage actively in learning activities and achieve higher levels of reading proficiency. Research has consistently demonstrated that motivation, interest, and positive attitudes are closely associated with reading achievement.

The study also highlighted the importance of positive teacher-student relationships. Teachers who foster supportive and caring classroom environments help learners feel secure, valued, and motivated. Such relationships contribute to better academic outcomes and encourage active participation in learning.

Overall, the findings indicate that effective teaching practices, parental involvement, remediation programs, learner motivation, and supportive classroom environments collectively contributed to the strong reading performance demonstrated by the majority of the Kindergarten learners.

Relationship Between Reading Readiness and Reading Performance

One of the primary objectives of the study was to determine whether reading readiness was significantly related to reading performance among Kindergarten learners.

The statistical analysis revealed that there was no significant relationship between reading readiness and reading performance. The computed correlation coefficient was $r = 0.294$ with a p-value of 0.059, which exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the relationship was not statistically significant.

This finding indicates that reading readiness, as measured by cognitive ability and intellectual readiness, did not significantly predict how well learners performed in reading. In other words, learners who demonstrated higher levels of reading readiness did not necessarily achieve higher reading performance, while some learners with lower readiness scores still performed well in reading.

The results suggest that reading readiness alone is insufficient to explain learners' academic performance. While cognitive abilities contribute to learning, numerous other factors influence reading achievement.

One possible explanation is that learners develop reading skills through experiences and support received after admission to Kindergarten. Effective instruction, parental involvement, learner motivation, classroom environment, and access to learning resources may have compensated for lower readiness levels among some learners.

The findings are consistent with previous studies indicating that cognitive ability is not the sole determinant of academic achievement. Research by Estes, Rivera, and Matthew (2010) found that social skills and environmental influences significantly contributed to academic performance. Similarly, Braaten and Norman (2006) emphasized that intelligence tests provide only one indicator of future academic success, while factors such as quality instruction, parental support, motivation, and educational opportunities play equally important roles.

Ormrod (2010) also argued that intelligence test scores alone cannot fully predict school achievement because learning is influenced by various contextual and motivational factors. Children's cognitive abilities continue to develop over time, especially when supported by stimulating learning environments and encouraging adults.

These findings reinforce the notion that learning is a multifaceted process influenced by both individual characteristics and environmental factors. Although reading readiness remains important, educational stakeholders should recognize that children's academic outcomes depend on a combination of cognitive, emotional, social, instructional, and environmental influences.

The qualitative findings revealed several challenges experienced by Kindergarten teachers in teaching reading.

High Learning Expectations

Teachers reported feeling pressure due to the high learning expectations established for Kindergarten learners. They recognized the responsibility of ensuring that learners acquire advanced reading skills and meet the standards set by the school and standardized assessments.

Many teachers expressed concern about achievement test results because they felt accountable for learners' performance. The pressure was intensified by the school's accreditation standards and commitment to maintaining academic excellence.

To cope with these demands, teachers pursued professional development opportunities. They attended seminars, participated in training programs, and enrolled in graduate studies to enhance their teaching competencies. These activities broadened their knowledge and equipped them with more effective instructional strategies for teaching young learners.

Teachers also utilized various learning resources, including books, online materials, and digital platforms such as Genyo E-Learning. These resources enabled them to create engaging and differentiated instructional activities that addressed learners' diverse needs.

Another challenge identified by teachers was the increasing emphasis on standardized assessments in Kindergarten. Teachers acknowledged the value of such assessments in measuring student achievement and identifying learners needing intervention. However, they also expressed concerns that excessive focus on testing could create stress for both learners and parents.

Despite these concerns, teachers recognized that standardized tests provide useful information for evaluating instructional effectiveness and planning future interventions. Assessment results help identify strengths and weaknesses, monitor progress, and ensure learners meet established academic standards.

Teachers also found it challenging to teach children with varying abilities, learning styles, behaviors, and developmental levels. Differences in reading fluency, comprehension, vocabulary, attention span, and behavior required teachers to adapt instruction continually.

To address these challenges, teachers employed differentiated instruction and individualized learning approaches. They designed varied activities that accommodated diverse learning needs and provided opportunities for all learners to experience success.

Parental cooperation was identified as a critical factor in addressing these challenges. Teachers emphasized the importance of immediate parental responses to feedback regarding learners' academic performance and behavior. Strong teacher-parent partnerships facilitated timely interventions and reinforced positive learning behaviors both at home and in school.

Parents likewise reported several challenges related to supporting their children's reading development.

Managing High Academic Expectations

Many parents initially felt apprehensive about the high learning expectations imposed on Kindergarten learners. However, most eventually observed positive outcomes as their children became more interested in reading and demonstrated rapid learning progress.

Parents generally viewed these expectations positively because they believed they prepared children for Grade 1 and promoted academic readiness. Nevertheless, some parents whose children lacked prior literacy experiences found the expectations difficult to manage.

Parents employed several strategies to support reading development. Storytelling emerged as one of the most commonly used methods. By reading stories and creating positive literacy experiences, parents encouraged children's interest in reading while strengthening communication skills.

Parents appreciated the school's remediation programs and actively supported their children's participation. They recognized that remedial instruction provided individualized assistance that helped struggling learners improve their reading skills and catch up with classmates.

Parents utilized worksheets, flashcards, sight-word exercises, and reading activities provided by teachers. These resources enabled them to reinforce classroom learning and help children practice reading skills at home.

Regular communication with teachers also allowed parents to receive specific feedback about their children's strengths and weaknesses. This information guided their efforts in providing appropriate support and intervention.

Developing Study Habits and Discipline

Some parents struggled to encourage children who showed limited interest in studying or reading. To address this challenge, parents implemented reward systems and established structured reading schedules. By associating reading with positive reinforcement, they motivated children to participate more actively in learning activities.

Research supports the effectiveness of self-discipline and structured learning routines in promoting academic success. Parents who consistently reinforced study habits and reading practices helped their children develop greater responsibility and motivation toward learning.

The findings demonstrate that most Kindergarten learners exhibited satisfactory reading readiness and strong reading performance. Although reading readiness was not significantly correlated with reading achievement, learners generally performed well due to the combined influence of effective teaching practices, parental involvement, remediation programs, learner motivation, and supportive learning environments.

The study highlights that academic success cannot be explained solely by cognitive readiness. Rather, it is shaped by a complex interaction of individual, instructional, familial, and environmental factors. Teachers and parents play complementary roles in nurturing children's literacy development, and their collaboration is essential in fostering reading success among young learners.

The results emphasize the importance of providing supportive educational experiences, meaningful instruction, early interventions, and strong home-school partnerships to ensure that children develop the literacy skills necessary for future academic achievement.

Conclusions:

Reading performance is not associated with reading readiness. It is not the sole determinant in the reading performance of a child. The Kindergarten learners were mentally ready to learn since most of them underwent pre-school. Others were not yet ready due to the extent of support may not have fully given by the adults. There are other factors that can influence the child's reading performance such as the teachers' commitment and dedication in teaching, the instructional approaches used, learners' attitude and interest to learn, remediation given to learners, giving immediate, clear and specific feedback to parents on their child's performance and parents' involvement and support in their child's learning.

Dr. Arnold Gesell's Maturation Theory of child development stated that children are expected to show certain attitude and abilities according to a maturational timetable. It revealed otherwise, some children may not even go through all the stages and may not reach the state of maturity but can still satisfactorily perform well in school. Others may perform lower than what is presumed.

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